

Measuring the Coolness of Folding Mobile Phones

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Abstract—In 2019, we have seen the launch of different folding mobiles. Many companies are planning to develop folding mobiles, and this trend will continue in the coming years. So, the question is how cool are the folding mobiles? This research aims to find the coolness of three folding mobiles: Huawei Mate X, Samsung Galaxy Fold, and Sony Xperia Flex. To measure the coolness, we considered five factors: desirability, rebelliousness, aesthetic, hedonic, and overall coolness. We didn't consider the usability factor due to the unavailability of the expensive folding mobile for each participant. The data was collected by using Google online forms. A total of 300 peoples participated in the survey (100 for each folding mobile phone). The results of this study conclude that the overall coolness of the folding mobile is higher (6.14 for Huawei Mate X; 5.97 for Samsung Galaxy Fold; 5.89 for Sony Xperia Flex). Furthermore, the Cronbach Alpha value for the Huawei Mate X is .953. It is .950 for the Samsung Galaxy Fold and .949 for the Sony Xperia Flex. These Cronbach values suggest that a cool questionnaire is also a suitable tool for measuring the coolness of folding mobiles.

Keywords— coolness, aesthetic, hedonic, desirability, rebelliousness

I. INTRODUCTION

Coolness has become an important aspect for measuring the success of a product. The coolness is closely related to a pleasant experience, positive attitude, and style. Different factors of a product are analysed for being cool. The perception of coolness is subjective, and it is different from person to person. It is based not only on individual opinion but also on the communities we belong to, such as culture, sex, political and social groups. Through an interest in all different aspects and systems, people's perspective about coolness is made. Different people have different ideas about what is cool and presentable; for example, one group of people like to listen Eminem, whereas other people like to listen to Johnny Cash.

These communities have been formed because of the same taste in music [1, 2, 3]. This coolness prescription ties the people or similar groups together and separates them based on different interests and beliefs [4, 5]. Here we cannot conclude or say anything about the coolness of a product or a person without taking into consideration the society and community they are part of and living in. The literature argues that coolness is something that someone can perceive or recognize based on what someone can observe at that time [6, 7]. Coolness is not something we need to think about much. People only consider some qualities to be cool, which they seem are relevant to them.

Since coolness is used to characterize many products, designing for coolness has become progressively important for interaction designers and HCI researchers. While talking about coolness, the first question that arises in our mind is how to measure this important aspect? There is a need to develop some specific tools and techniques that can help measure the coolness of the product. In the cool literature, one can now find new papers that can explain some tools related to the coolness of the product or how one can enhance it. For example, through card sorting, one can analyse the coolness of the product. [8 9]. Coolness can be measured by using a questionnaire [10, 11]. There is a lot of requirement of important techniques and tools that will measure the product coolness. If we look in the past, the problem was the same regarding the quality of the products. In (2014), Sundar et al. [10] designed a questionnaire sample with 15 items that calculate coolness using factors related to attractiveness, originality, and subculture. In (2016), Bruun et al. [12] designed a questionnaire that consists of 16 items that track the difference between inner coolness and outer coolness. He measured the perceived inner coolness of interactive

products by using factors related to usability, desirability, rebelliousness, attractiveness, and aesthetics. All these studies gradually made enhancements in the development of factors.

This paper attempts to measure the coolness of three folding mobile phones (Huawei Mate X, Samsung Galaxy Fold, and Sony Xperia). To measure the coolness, we have utilized the questionnaire that has been developed by Bruun et al., 2016 [12]. We have used five factors; desirability, rebelliousness, classic aesthetic, hedonic, and overall cool. This article has been organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the cool questionnaire. Section 3 presents the research methodology. Section 4 discusses the results. Section 5 discusses the research question, while Section 6 conclusion of this study.

II. THE COOL QUESTIONNAIRE

Creating helpful questionnaires needs meticulous statistical confirmation and exploration to ensure robustness; for example, it is important to calculate items reliably. To calculate the cool questionnaire, one can apply the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) by considering the example of [13], which created expressive aesthetics questionnaires. EFA is based on a process where data collection technique (questionnaire) items are erased from starting a pool of items based on the point by which they participate to calculate the basic factor. An item's participation is calculated through two-factor loadings, where a high loading means that there is a connection or the similarity is present with the given factor. But if an item has a low loading (in our case, below a cut off level of 0.6) on all the factors, then that item should be removed. This is an important process, or you can say the iterative process. According to Lavie and Tractinsky (2004), with removing the items, another EFA gets conducted on a new dataset until each item that gets remained has a high level of correlation with a single factor.

It is significant to note that reliability depends on having the items similar to one factor, not with multiple factors. This leaves behind the concept of 'multicollinearity,' which should be low. CFA is of confirmatory nature. Whereas the EFA is all about exploring, removing, or adding items, depending on the emerging factors. In CFA, the loadings are utilized in the same way as in the EFA. In CFA, there is the covariance between the factors that how they are correlated. A factor model's reliability is calculated by a range of fit indices, whether the factor structure is usable and reliable or not. Where the EFA is about exploring (removing and sometimes adding items, depending on the emerging factors), the CFA is applied to make a final validation of these factors and the items that measure them [14]. In CFA, the notion of loadings is used in the same way as in EFA described above. In CFA, there are item loadings on factors and covariance between factors denoting how variances between any two pairs of factors are correlated. A factor model's goodness is determined by a range of fit indices, which collectively indicate whether or not the factor structure is appropriate and reliable. To ensure the validity, it is hard to say that CFA is not conducted on the same pattern as EFA; otherwise, you will end up ensuring the factor model process on the same given data on which all of this was derived and

thereby run the risk of inflated model fit measures. If we see in CFA, there are many measures to determine the model fit.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main goal of this research is to find the coolness of three folding mobiles. The research question is as follow:

RQ1: Is Huawei Mate X folding mobile cooler than Samsung Galaxy Fold and Sony Xperia Flex?

In order to approach this research, we have used a survey methodology. The survey has been conducted online by using Google forms.

A. Questionnaire Items

Coolness can be divided into inner and outer cool [15]. The inner coolness explains someone's character, whereas outer coolness explains the product's appearance and physical style. Inner coolness depicts someone's personality, and outer coolness reflects the personality traits that help people in one way or another. Likewise, if someone says that 'James Dean' in the famous movie 'Rebel without a Cause' looks cooler. It does not mean that he looks cool by the clothes he's wearing but also includes his style and personality. Here, if we take an iPhone example, it represents its physical appearance (outer cool) and describes its qualities, features, and characteristics (inner cool). Inner and outer coolness is closely related to each other; inner reflects characteristics and qualities, while the outer cool reflects physical appearance. Outer cool is important as well as there is a need to focus on the inner coolness.

In this study, we have considered both inner and outer coolness. To measure the perceived coolness of folding mobiles, we have used a well-established questionnaire developed by Bruun et al., 2016 (See Table 1 [12]). We measured five factors: desirability, rebelliousness, classic aesthetic, hedonic, and overall cool. We did not consider the usability factor because of the expensive foldable phone's unavailability for each user. The cool questionnaire can be seen in Fig 1.

Desirability	This device can make me better	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device can make me look in control of things	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device can make me look good	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device can make me happy	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
Rebelliousness	This device moves against the current	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device is different	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device is outside the ordinary	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device stands apart from similar devices	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
Per-Usability	This device is simple to use	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device is easy to use	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device is easy to operate	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
Classic	This device has clear design	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	This device has clean	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
	I find this device	plain	<input type="radio"/>	eye catching						
Hedonic	I find this device	boring	<input type="radio"/>	interesting						
	I judge this device to be	dull	<input type="radio"/>	exciting						
	I judge this device to be	unimaginative	<input type="radio"/>	creative						
	This device is cool	strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
When I think of cool things, devices like this come to mind		strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						
If I made a list of cool things, this device would be on it		strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree						

Fig 1. The cool questionnaire

B. Data Collection

The data has been collected from the eRozgaar center, situated in different cities of Pakistan. eRozgaar Program is an

initiative of PITB (Punjab Information Technology Board) that provides technical skill training to the different levels of students. A total of 300 (100 for 3 folding mobiles study) participated in the survey. They all are well aware of using mobile phones, computers and browsing the internet.

Participants detail for Study 1 (Huawei Mate X): In study 1, one hundred participants filled the questionnaire. Almost 1.1% are in between the age of 13-17, 52.7% are in between the age of 18-24, 42.9% are between the age of 25-34, 2.2% are in the age of 35-44, and 1.1% are in between the age of 45-54. Of which 54% are males, and 46% are females.

Participants detail for Study 2 (Samsung Galaxy Fold): In study 2, one hundred peoples participated in the survey. Almost 1% are between the ages of 13-17, 54.1% are between the ages of 18 and 24, 43.9% are between the ages of 25 and 34, and 1% are between 35 and 44. Of which 58% are males, and 42% are females.

Participants detail for Study 3 (Sony Xperia Flex): In study 3, In study 3, another hundred peoples participated in the survey. About 55% are between 18 and 24, 44% are between the age of 25 and 34, and 1% are between 35 and 44. Of which 53% are males, and 47% are females.

IV. RESULTS

To analyze the data, we have performed a descriptive analysis. In the descriptive analysis, we measured the mean and standard deviation. Furthermore, we also calculated the Cronbach alpha. We used the IBM SPSS Statistics tool to measure the mean, standard deviation, and the Cronbach Alpha values. SPSS tool automatically calculates results by taking data from Excel sheets. The results of each of the folding mobile are presented in the following subsections.

A. Study 1: Huawei Mate X

In study 1, one hundred people rate the Huawei Mate X folding mobile by choosing an option given in the questionnaire. The cool questionnaire is available on request. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the Huawei Mate X is .953. The mean and the standard deviation values for each of the questionnaire items can be seen in Table 1.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.953	.954	17

Table 1 Cronbach's alpha values for Huawei Mate X mobile

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
This device can make me better	6.0600	1.40576	100
This device can make me look in	5.8100	1.51554	100

control of things			
This device can make me look good	6.0500	1.28216	100
This device can make me happy	6.2200	1.19409	100
This device moves against the current	5.9000	1.17637	100
This device is different	6.2600	1.11573	100
This device is outside the ordinary	5.9800	1.42120	100
This device stands apart from similar devices	6.0100	1.41774	100
This device has clear design	6.2000	1.20605	100
This device has clean design	6.2800	1.10170	100
I found this device	6.2100	1.34311	100
I found this device	6.3200	1.17103	100
I judge this device to be	6.2800	1.11083	100
I judge this device to be	6.2600	1.29973	100
This device is cool	6.3000	1.19342	100
When I think of cool things, devices like this come to mind.	6.2100	1.05692	100
If I made a list of cool things, this device would be on it.	6.0200	1.29474	100

Table 2 Mean and the Std. Deviation values for each Questionnaire items

B. Study 2: Samsung Galaxy Fold

Study 2 is related to Samsung Galaxy Fold. One hundred people rate the Samsung Galaxy fold mobile by choosing an option given in the cool questionnaire. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the Samsung Galaxy Fold is .950; see Table 3. The mean and the standard deviation values for each of the questionnaire items can be seen in Table 4.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.950	.951	17

Table 3 Cronbach's alpha values for Samsung Galaxy Fold

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
This device can make me better	5.7200	1.67018	100
This device can make me look in control of things	5.8800	1.38739	100
This device can make me look good	6.0600	1.46211	100
This device can make me happy	5.8700	1.54171	100
This device moves against the current	5.6400	1.40360	100
This device is different	6.1200	1.20000	100
This device is outside the ordinary	5.9000	1.43900	100
This device stands apart from similar devices	5.8000	1.60806	100
This device has clear design	6.1400	1.23108	100
This device has clean design	6.1100	1.25445	100
I found this device	5.7200	1.67622	100

I found this device	6.0100	1.48048	100
I judge this device to be	5.9600	1.46969	100
I judge this device to be	5.9700	1.54694	100
This device is cool	6.1900	1.39277	100
When I think of cool things, devices like this come to mind.	5.8600	1.48786	100
If I made a list of cool things, this device would be on it.	5.7800		100

Table 4 Mean and the Std. Deviation values for each Questionnaire items

C. Study 3: Sony Xperia Flex

Study 3 is related to Sony Xperia Flex. One hundred respondents rate the Sony Xperia Flex by choosing an option given in the cool questionnaire. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the Sony Xperia Flex is .949. The mean and the standard deviation values for each of the questionnaire items can be seen in Table 6.

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.949	.951	17

Table 5 Cronbach's alpha values for Sony Xperia Flex

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
This device can make me better	5.6600	1.54541	100
This device can make me look in control of things	5.5100	1.51421	100
This device can make me look good	5.9600	1.42786	100
This device can make me happy	5.8000	1.52422	100
This device moves	5.5100	1.27521	100

against the current			
This device is different	5.9100	1.18998	100
This device is outside the ordinary	5.6800	1.47628	100
This device stands apart from similar devices	5.4900	1.52086	100
This device has clear design	6.0600	1.22119	100
This device has clean design	5.9600	1.27065	100
I found this device	6.0400	1.39204	100
I found this device	5.8000	1.51757	100
I judge this device to be	5.9900	1.28311	100
I judge this device to be	5.9100	1.36400	100
This device is cool	6.0500	1.13150	100
When I think of cool things, devices like this come to mind.	5.8400	1.21206	100
If I made a list of cool things, this device would be on it.	5.8000	1.31809	100

Table 6 Mean and the Std. Deviation values for each Questionnaire items

V. DISCUSSION

The main goal of this research was to find the coolness of Huawei Mate X, Samsung Galaxy Fold, and Sony Xperia Flex. All the respondents rated the folding mobiles by choosing an option from the cool questionnaire. The mean value for the overall coolness of Huawei Mate X is 6.14, while it is 5.97 for Samsung Galaxy Fold and 5.89 for Sony Xperia Flex. The second factor, desirability mean value is (M = 5.99 for Huawei Mate X; M = 5.9 for Samsung Galaxy Ford and M = 5.74 for Sony Xperia Flex). The third-factor rebelliousness mean value is (M = 5.99 for Huawei Mate X; M = 5.85 for Samsung Galaxy Fold and M = 5.66 for Sony Xperia Flex). The fourth factor, the classic mean value is (M = 6.21 for Huawei Mate X; M = 6.13

for Samsung Galaxy Fold and M = 6.01 for Sony Xperia Flex). The fifth factor, the hedonic mean value is (M = 6.22 for Huawei Mate X; M = 5.94 for Samsung Galaxy Fold and M = 5.94 for Sony Xperia Flex). The overall mean and their standard deviation can be seen in Table 7.

	Huawei Mate X		Samsung Galaxy Fold		Sony Xperia	
	MEAN	STDEV	MEAN	STDEV	MEAN	STDEV
OVERALL COOLNESS	6.142857	1.217864	5.979592	1.298302	5.891358	1.219905
DESIRABILITY	5.99449	1.39255	5.905612	1.482643	5.74026	1.449033
REBELLIOUSNESS	5.991758	1.32259	5.84949	1.428715	5.668519	1.386166
CLASSIC	6.214286	1.172057	6.127755	1.247111	6.014815	1.222376
HEDONIC	6.222527	1.26945	5.94898	1.487355	5.942593	1.328453

Table 7 Mean and standard deviation values of Cool factors for three folding mobiles

Fig 2. Graphical representation of each cool factors

The research question of this research is as follow:
RQ1: Is Huawei Mate X folding mobile cooler than Samsung Galaxy Fold and Sony Xperia Flex?

This study shows that the participants liked the folding mobile idea and consider all the folding mobile cool. There is a slight difference between the values of the three mobile. So, we can't say clearly that Huawei Mate X is cooler than the Samsung Galaxy Fold and Sony Xperia Flex.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research aims to find the coolness of three folding mobiles: Huawei Mate X, Samsung Galaxy Fold, and Sony Xperia Flex. Folding mobile is a new phenomenon. There is a need to investigate if people would love this idea and consider it

cool. In order to approach this research, we have used the survey methodology. We measured five coolness factors: desirability, rebelliousness, classic aesthetic, hedonic, and overall cool. We didn't consider the usability factor due to the unavailability of the expensive folding mobile for each participant. The data was collected by using Google online forms. A total of 300 people participated in the survey (100 for each folding mobile phone). The results of this study conclude that the overall coolness of the folding mobile is higher (6.14 for Huawei Mate X; 5.97 for Samsung Galaxy Fold; 5.89 for Sony Xperia Flex). Furthermore, the Cronbach Alpha value for the Huawei Mate X is .953. It is .950 for the Samsung Galaxy Fold and .949 for the Sony Xperia Flex. These Cronbach values suggest that a cool questionnaire is also a suitable tool for measuring the coolness of folding mobiles.

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